

the F₁, 275 panicles of the F₂).

The F₁ population, with a wide range of variation (mean 76% Pb, 75% Sb), markedly exceeded the high parent (56%). The F₂ population had a continuous distribution—10-90% Pb and 20- to 90% Sb, mean of 60% Pb and 59% Sb. The curve was unimodal, but skewed somewhat negatively (see figure). Only a few plants exceeded the lower parental limit and 20% exceeded the upper limit of IR30, indicating that multiple genes with opposite effects were operating.

The dominance effect (Pb - 34.0, Sb - 34.2) was 2-3 times higher than the additive effects (Pb - 16.4, Sb - 12.0). The potence ratio was more than 2 (Pb - 2.16, Sb - 2.60), indicating over-dominance of genes governing this trait. The effective factor pairs estimate was

Distribution and means of parents, F₁, and F₂ plants of IR30/IR32385-37-3-3-3 cross, by high density grain index. IRRI, 1987 wet season.

0.58 for Pb and 1.26 for Sb, indicating that the trait is controlled by a few genes of the polymeric model. The degree of heterosis was 86.76 (Pb), 69.96 (Sb); heterobeltiosis was 33.22 (Pb) and 33.92 (Sb).

The heritability estimate was very high, more than 80%. Thus, selections for more high density grain may be effective in early segregating generations such as F₃ or F₄. We have selected 40 F₃ lines to evaluate in the F₄. □

Yield potential

Performance of new Bw rice varieties compared to Bg 400-1 in Sri Lanka

A. H. G. Mithrasena and P. E. Peiris,
Regional Agricultural Research Centre,
Bomuwela, Sri Lanka

Bg 400-1 (Ob 678//IR20/H4), bred at Central Rice Breeding Centre, Batalagoda, Sri Lanka, is a very popular 4- to 4 1/2-mo variety because it adapts to diverse environments. Under good management, it has produced 7 t/ha in the low country wet zone of Sri Lanka.

However, panicle sterility, particularly in the yala season (Apr-Aug), has drastically reduced yields. To find a replacement for Bg 400-1, we evaluated lines in yala 1986 (Apr-Aug) and maha 1986/87 (Sep-Mar) in farmers' fields.

Bw 295-5 (Ob 678/Bw 254-1) and sister lines Bw 271-1 and Bw 271-2 (Bw 259-4/Bw 100) were chosen for field testing and comparison with Bg 400-1.

Trial sites represented the varying production potentials of diverse soil conditions in the low country wet zone.

Rice was wet seeded at 100 kg/ha in plots 6 × 4.5 m, with 30 cm space between plots.

Fertilizer and agrochemicals were applied as recommended in farmer-managed trials guided by field staff. Plot yields were converted to t/ha at 14% moisture level.

Average yields of the four varieties did not differ significantly. However, yields varied greatly within and across environments (13 locations in yala and 18 in maha), partly because of differing

soil fertility and farmer management levels.

Regression analysis showed that Bw 295-5 is as well adapted to a range of environments as is Bg 400-1. Bw 295-5 is similar to Bg 400-1 in plant height, tiller number, panicle length, grain color, and grain size.

Results show Bw 295-5 should be favorably considered. It is better than Bw 271-1 and Bw 271-2 in areas where Bg 400-1 is currently grown. □

Breeding methods

Substituting urea and boric acid for gibberellic acid in hybrid rice seed production

M. N. Prasad, S. S. Virmani, and A. D. Gamutan, Plant Breeding Department, IRRI

The growth regulator gibberellic acid (GA₃) is used in hybrid rice seed production in China to increase panicle exertion, stigma exertion, and plant height and to synchronize flowering between primary and secondary tillers.

That helps increase outcrossing on the male sterile line and hybrid seed yield. But GA₃ is expensive (\$8/20 g) in countries outside China. When applied at 30-45 g/ha, costs soar. GA₃ also increases plant height, which induces lodging. The extra exerted panicles can break during the wet season (WS) under torrential rains and strong winds.

We looked for a suitable substitute for GA₃. Hybrid seed production experiments with sorghum and pearl millet have shown the effectiveness of urea and boric acid sprays in increasing hybrid seed yields. These chemicals are available and cheap throughout the